

Figure S1: The influence of the ability of NPs to induce superoxide generation as measured in an acellular EPR assay on the different biomarkers of effects. The shading indicates the lowest (light grey) to highest (dark grey) response of an NP (relative to each other) for each of the biomarkers. The arrows indicate an increase (↗) or decrease (↖) with decreasing amount of superoxide generation.